

ATTENTION TO WOMEN IN AN INNOVATIVE
SOCIETY**Tursunboyev Zukhrob Tokhir ugli**

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a scientific and philosophical analysis of the innovative processes occurring in the social, cultural, and spiritual spheres of women's lives. The study examines the concepts of "pressure and violence" and "domestic violence," their types, conceptual foundations, and legal mechanisms for prevention. Furthermore, it highlights the philosophical and anthropological aspects of the conformity factor in preventing pressure and violence within family relationships. The article also emphasizes the significance of innovative approaches in the system of social protection for women, demonstrating the integration of national values and contemporary innovations. The results of the study are theoretically and practically important for enhancing women's social status, protecting them from violence, and ensuring social stability..

Introduction: One of the reasons for the accelerated development of innovative processes in the system of social protection for women is global changes in the world—such as the development of the Internet and the formation of a unified economic and information space. The adoption, application, and creation of advanced technologies in all areas of social life is, on the one hand, a consequence of globalization and, on the other hand, an expression of the striving for improvement that arises in the process of sustainable development. Efforts to create an innovative model aimed at increasing the effectiveness of various systems, particularly the system of social protection for women, are also examples of this drive to positively transform existing conditions.

The scientific analysis of the concept of innovation supports this view. Innovation is the activity of society members aimed at creating material and spiritual wealth based on new ways of thinking, resulting in increased efficiency in the operation of existing systems. Recognizing, understanding, and selecting the most relevant innovations, applying them to appropriate fields, regulating them, and managing them properly are essential yet challenging tasks. In the context of social protection for women, innovative approaches are particularly important, as they enhance the effectiveness of system management.

Another essential feature of innovation-driven approaches to socio-economic development is that isolated application in a single field rarely yields the expected positive results. Innovation develops rapidly and achieves the desired outcome only when it

encompasses all areas of society. Moreover, innovative processes in one sector of social development influence other sectors. This dialectical process continues uninterrupted. The path of innovative development occurs as system elements evolve based on their potential, acquire new characteristics, or incorporate new components into the system.

The emergence of innovation is a gradual process of development that moves from simple to complex in a lawful manner. Every system has a mechanism of self-development, where old elements or phenomena are replaced by innovations, and the structural components of the system are regularly updated—a characteristic of development. Innovations arise on a new basis, with new structures and elements. As the number of these elements increases, existing systems are renewed and enriched with new components.

Literature Review and Methodology

The social-philosophical and sociological aspects of preventing domestic violence in Uzbekistan have been extensively studied by scholars such as N.M. Latipova, O. Musurmonova, N.R. Nishonova, M.X. Kholmatova, G. Matkarimova, X. Nasrullayeva, N. Jo'rayeva, M. Nurmatova, E. Sultonova, S.X. Safayeva, Sh. Sodiqova, G.J. G'aniyeva, and M.Q. G'afforova. These studies focus on preventing family conflicts and ensuring social and moral stability within the family unit.

Among scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States, L.I. Amanbayeva, A.V. Belyayev, M.V. Bogomaz, L.S. Vygotsky, Dj. Karpara, V.A. Sitarov, and G.K. Selevkolar explored the socio-psychological aspects of preventing domestic violence. Furthermore, G.M. Andreyeva, V.V. Antipov, L.P. Bogdanova, A. Varga, I.F. Dementyeva, T.R. Kirimov, P.R. Novikov, Ye.G. Silyayeva, and L.B. Shneyder conducted studies on interpersonal relationships within families, highlighting the necessity of psychological services and defining the main requirements for counseling.

International studies have also addressed gender approaches and gender identity issues in combating domestic violence. Scholars such as R. Connell, P. Bourdieu, Dj. Scott, V. Spijker-Peterson, and O.A. Voronina analyzed these issues from a constructive paradigm perspective. Additionally, leading researchers like N. Najib, E. Helen, A. Kitchen, M. Kowalski, D. Rutz, and L. Husni examined domestic violence in the context of international humanitarian law, developing legal solutions and recommendations for mitigating psychological and emotional distress among affected women.

Results and Discussion

As emphasized by the President of Uzbekistan, raising future scholars and specialists requires first and foremost nurturing healthy, highly educated, and morally sound mothers. Reforming the education system from preschool to higher education is essential to enhance the knowledge and moral level of youth and society as a whole. Lack of knowledge and moral education inevitably leads to ignorance and misguidance.

Previously, the neighborhood (mahalla) system was limited in identifying the state of families or the needs of women in vulnerable groups. Currently, the Social Protection Concept developed under the State Program reflects innovative approaches in social protection, including:

- Improving the social benefits system and expanding coverage for low-income families.
- Establishing updated criteria for identifying vulnerable populations.

- Reforming outdated rules for assigning benefits and ensuring a transparent and fair process.

- Providing subsidies from the State Budget for initial payments or interest on mortgage loans for individuals in need of improved housing conditions.

- Enhancing stationary medical and social services for the elderly and persons with disabilities in “Muruvvat” and “Saxovat” homes.

- Reviewing the amount of social payments in accordance with current needs.

These measures demonstrate an innovative approach to preventing domestic violence and fostering a stable social environment in society.

- The coordination of social protection and social services provided to citizens by the state, which are currently distributed across various ministries and agencies;

- The development of a special program to ensure the social adaptation of young people, particularly girls, raised in “orphanages,” especially in terms of employment and housing.

In such conditions, the emergence of new values contributes to the development of the intellectual potential of society. Innovations become a criterion of human activity and take a place in the system of contemporary values. In the development of Uzbekistan, individuals with modern thinking, innovative values, and potential can play a significant role. Advanced individuals, who meet the standards established in society, are initiative-driven, and possess managerial skills, can lead high-potential individuals and organize their activities, thereby contributing to the formation of an innovative society.

Innovation, while being an objective process, is also based on the activity of subjects and is driven by them. The subjects of innovation processes include innovators and various idea generators, whose goals and aspirations are aligned with the process. As a result of the development of innovations, changes occur in the system of values that have been formed over centuries and hold significant importance in human life.

The introduction, dissemination, and assimilation of innovations lead to the renewal and modernization of various sectors of society in a distinctive manner, and as a result, all areas of society acquire an innovative character. The application of innovations in all spheres of social life lays the foundation for rapid socio-economic, political, legal, scientific, technological, and cultural-spiritual development of society.

The sociological aspects of building an innovative society are directly related to the innovative environment, the predictive concept of leadership, social opinion, the alignment of corporate interests and goals, and the support of innovative group activities.

In the lives of women, in the socio-cultural and spiritual spheres, a trend is observed where the desire to preserve national values and traditions as a stable factor coexists with the increasing drive to introduce innovations and embrace changes. Addressing the tasks facing society is closely linked to human capital, and in our country, this issue is being implemented as a priority direction of state policy. Indeed, the rapidly advancing innovative approaches in the country form the basis of socially sustainable development, and the prospects and outcomes of social protection for women are largely connected to the development of women as individuals, i.e., human capital.

The factors influencing the improvement of the social protection system for women can be classified as follows:

1.The existing social environment in society – the availability of conditions necessary for social development, including healthcare, employment, and timely development of the education system;

2.The socio-cultural and spiritual life of society – the development of skills among society and its members to accept and utilize scientific innovations.

Thirdly, the value system – high human regard for women, their recognition as active subjects of knowledge, science, and innovation, and the significant social attention given to them.

Thus, civil society provides the necessary environment for the development of innovations. From this perspective, the creation of a completely new, innovative model of social protection for women is implemented as an objective and necessary process within the framework of the deep reforms currently being carried out in the country.

Conclusion

A key factor in the rise of the social status of women in the state and society is, without a doubt, the five priority areas outlined in the Action Strategy for Further Development of Uzbekistan, which wisely determine both our current and future sustainable development. Positive changes in the social life of our people, carried out in close connection with economic reforms, along with increased attention to these issues, have distinctive characteristics and contribute to the continuous improvement and strengthening of the social protection system, thereby creating a solid foundation for the country's economic progress.

The people-oriented policy pursued by our state primarily aims to strengthen human resources, elevate human capital to a new level, and ensure development aligned with the interests, aspirations, and needs of every citizen. In conditions where this activity becomes a comprehensive social movement, effectively protecting the population becomes one of the most important tasks in a market economy. In this context, the innovative model of the social protection system is particularly significant, as it focuses on timely addressing social problems that require operational solutions in society during the ongoing period of economic reforms..

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